

Research Paper

Doing age in the workplace: Exploring age categorisation in performance appraisal

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ABSTRACT

Ageism in the manager–employee relationship is one of the main obstacles towards an age-inclusive workplace. Ageism in the labour market is rooted in the use of age as an organising principle of employment relations. This article contributes to the study of ageism in the workplace by investigating how stages of life, as normalised age categories, are mobilised through discursive practices in performance appraisals. Based on the analysis of video recordings of actual performance appraisal interviews at an Italian labour union, three discursive ways of ‘doing age’ – or of how age, as a constructed social category, is performed and enacted – were identified: quantification (e.g. number of years in the organisation), ‘ageing within the organisation’ and age-group membership identification (e.g. ‘young’ vs. ‘old’). The analysis suggests that stages of life categories and age attributes are ‘done’ in social interactions and employed by both employees and managers as shared culture to sustain ongoing organisational activities, thereby reproducing discriminatory age norms and stereotypes. The study demonstrates how the ordering power of the stages of life categories is situated in organisational culture and challenges the implementation of equal and inclusive workplace policies.

Introduction

In the work context, age has been identified as an ordering element that influences transitions, workplace hierarchies and career stages (Fineman, 2014). Age also has divisive power in that it leads to the construction of age-based groups whose organisational features are rooted in stereotypical views of ageing as an impairing process (Thomas, Hardy, Cutcher, & Ainsworth, 2014). These ordering and divisive properties of age shape employer–employee relationships: for example, Loretto and White (2006) found that Scottish managers employed general negative stereotypes about older workers in making decisions about recruitment and performance evaluation. In line with Taylor and Walker (1998), they also argued that employers' attitudes towards older workers do not relate to specific characteristics of the work context itself but are, instead, based on the negative attributes socially attached to older persons as a homogenous group.

With policy makers and legislators advocating for interventions to prolong working life, research has analysed which age stereotypes are present in the labour force (Ainsworth & Hardy, 2007; Harris, Krygman, Waschenko, & Laliberte Rudman, 2018; Solem, 2020), how they

influence managerial processes, such as recruitment (McVittie, McKinlay, & Widdicombe, 2003; Riach, 2007), and which anti-ageist management practices can increase older workers' employment prospects (Clark & Ritter, 2020). From the perspective that advocates overcoming stereotypical views of older workers and gaining better understanding of the relational and discursive nature of ageism (Spedale, Coupland, & Tempest, 2014), several scholars have directed attention to the role of discourse and discursive resources in constructing ‘older workers’ and in the maintenance and reproduction of ageism and ageist practices (for a review on ageist discourses in working life, see Previtali, Keskinen, Niska, & Nikander, 2020). Within this strand of research, scholars have also focused on critically investigating and challenging the production of the ‘natural’ and ‘normal’ in organisational life by studying the normative notions of age (Krekula, 2019; Romaioli & Contarello, 2021).

Past research has significantly increased our understanding of how ageist ideologies play out in the construction of older age, both in general and in the context of work. This has fed scholarly interest in investigating the ‘othering process’ of older workers and in exposing how age as a category is constructed – often in intersection with gender (Krekula, Nikander, & Wilińska, 2018; McVittie et al., 2003). Attention

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has also been directed to exploring how policies supporting longer working life tend to homogenise older workers (Krekula & Vickerstaff, 2020), such as showing a privileged view of ageing, neglecting growing differences in longevity and widening inequalities.

Despite these research efforts, how age as a social category is constructed in the workplace at the micro level of interactions between managers and employees remains a largely unexplored topic. Extant studies focusing on mundane or medical social encounters have shed some light on the mechanisms underpinning the in-situ construction of older age, mostly relying on a fine-grained analysis of talk and bodies. For example, by analysing the everyday conversations of older women at a hair salon, Heinrichsmeier (2018) demonstrated that older age can be resisted or, indeed, invoked in the same conversation in relation to different interactional business: older women would use 'being old' to invite sympathy and justify claims about lack of energy in daily life but resist this very same categorisation by others when accounting for injuries in later life. The possibility that individuals can both adhere to and resist stereotypical views of ageing in the same conversation indicates the complex nature of the active negotiation of older age as identity in discursive encounters (Kaufman, 1986). More specifically, we suggest that although social interactions have been identified as the setting where ageist discourse and practices are situated, very little attention has been directed to investigating how they actually – indeed, agentically – shape the construction of age at work and their consequences for the construction of older workers' identity and equal employment relations.

Accordingly, our study draws from ethnomethodology and a discursive approach in applying the analytical framework of membership categorisation analysis (MCA) to investigate how the managers and employees of an Italian labour union 'did' age in the situated interaction of performance appraisal interviews (PAIs). Our findings are threefold. First, different categories of age – namely, the quantification of years on the job/in the organisation, 'ageing within the organisation' and age-group membership identification (e.g. 'old' vs. 'young') – are mobilised in the negotiation of different aspects of job evaluation. Second, age categorisation is done differently to account for positive or negative evaluation depending on the performance item under discussion and on the role of the appraiser or appraisee. Third, age categorisation is rooted in the shared culture of the social and organisational setting under study. Overall, our study contributes to the literature on ageism in the workplace by moving beyond the notion of social interaction as 'context' to reveal the complex dynamics of 'doing age' as a process of social construction.

Theoretical framework: the discursive construction of age groups in the workplace

Interest in ageing as a socially constructed phenomenon is one of the most enduring threads within social and cultural approaches to age studies (Coupland & Coupland, 1993). Discursive gerontology and studies that fall under this umbrella term (e.g. Heinrichsmeier, 2018; Nikander, 2009) challenge previous empiricism and support the notion that age should be conceptualised as an 'ongoing performance' (Cromdal, Danby, Emmison, Osvaldsson, & Cobb-Moore, 2018; Poullos, 2009) and as a social process informed by cultural knowledge (Nikander, 2002; Paoletti, 2020). At the intersection of social psychology and the discourse analysis tradition lies discursive psychology, the perspective adopted for this study (Potter and Wetherell, 1987). This theoretical and analytical approach 'treats talk and text as an object of study itself, and psychological concepts as socially managed and consequential in interaction' (Wiggins, 2017, p. 4). This means, in this approach, attitudes towards age(ing) are only accessible to researchers as actions in text and talk, whereas they would be regarded as reflections of inner psychological processes or states within cognitivist approaches.

The cultural connotation of age in the workplace is rooted in the organising power of this category (Fineman, 2014); this is typically

disregarded by professionals on the bases that age is a natural, biological feature of the workforce and that organisational processes are age-neutral. The ordering power of chronological age is, instead, constituted in the institutionalisation of the life course and through the normativity of life stages (Kohli, 2007). The standardisation power of life stages within organisations has been conceptualised as chrononormativity (Riach, Rumens, & Tyler, 2014). Chrononormativity is a critical way of 'exploring the temporal orders inscribed in organisational life' (Riach et al., 2014, p. 1678) and is grounded in the socially accepted idea that there is a 'right' time for clearly identifiable life and work stages, including partnering, parenting and caring and, respectively, career progression, promotion and flexible working. Krekula (2019) showed how the 'socio-temporal order' (p. 2290) in a Swedish foundry reduced the on and off time of older workers as an abnormality because mobility was normatively assigned to younger workers. This reveals how organisational practices and cultures are situated in wider societal age norms that are reflected and reinforced, as also shown by Spedale et al. (2014) in their investigation of the ageist use of broadcasting routines in a British television channel.

The discursive construction of older and younger workers is ideologically biased and materially affects those targeted by this labelling as well as those excluded – hence everyone (Ainsworth & Hardy, 2007). Stokoe and Edwards (2009) argued that identity categories, including age, are used by individuals to accomplish social actions and produce self-identities in everyday life. In organisations, categories such as 'older' or 'younger' workers become impersonal or supra-personal: they label a group of individuals with distinguishing characteristics and assign to them a specific set of rules, expectations and organisational purposes (Curchod, Patriotta, & Neysen, 2014). Berger (2006) highlighted how older workers often react to this degrading categorisation striving to maintain a positive self-image for the assigned category (e.g. older workers are wiser and are the repository of key organisational knowledge and expertise) or by embracing a new identity as, for example, 'retirees'. Younger workers are similarly discursively reproduced, as suggested by Pritchard and Whiting's (2014) study on how generations are enrolled as explanatory devices in online discussions in the UK about entitlement and responsibilities in the job market.

Overall, this extensive body of research has shed significant light on how age is socially constructed through discourse. This has, however, come at the expense of a more in-depth appreciation of the active role that situated social interactions play in the construction of age at work. We suggest that the interactional dimension of the process of the social construction of age is largely unexplored and, more specifically, that we could redress this gap by drawing from extant scholarship on categorisation work, stages of life (SOL) categories and age-in-interaction (i.e. 'doing age'), as these are particularly sensitive to interaction dynamics.

Analytical framework: 'doing age'

According to Nikander (2009), 'chronological age, lifespan categories and other interactional formulations of age surface and are made relevant for and by us, implicitly or explicitly, as we position each other or describe and account for our own and other's actions in various everyday settings' (p. 864). Interaction analysis in the form of conversation analysis and MCA has been successfully employed in exploring how age is interactionally constructed (Heinrichsmeier, 2018; Jolanki, 2004; Näslund, 2017; Nikander, 2000, 2009; Poullos, 2009; Thell & Jacobsson, 2016). Researchers have investigated age-in-interaction in different types of settings and showed how people negotiate different notions of age or age groups in interviews on ageing (i.e. turning 50 years old; Nikander, 2009), radio counselling (Thell & Jacobsson, 2016) and travel-booking (Ylänne-McEwen, 1999). However, the workplace as a site for 'doing' age remains under-explored. Studies on the micro-dynamics of interactions have uncovered how different interactants perform age differently despite sharing the same goal. For example, Coupland and Coupland (1994) showed that the mobilisation of older

age may lead to a more attentive focus on health issues in medical settings; in contrast, [Näslund \(2017\)](#) revealed that patients may reject older age categorisations to draw attention to their medical case.

From an analytical viewpoint, studying the categories in interaction reveals the speakers' culture and, overall, their understanding of reality. In many work-related situations, individual organisational actors engage in interaction sequences whereby they select specific categories – including, potentially, age – from a range of culturally available membership devices and use them to generate their own subjective interpretation of the world. In conversational turn-taking patterns, observers of these interaction sequences may align themselves with the proposed subjective positions by deploying the same (age) categorisation resources or, alternatively, may diverge from this interpretive line and select others ([Stokoe, 2012](#)). Past research on age-in-interaction has used the analytical tool of SOL categorisation to investigate how the life course is normatively perceived and persons share taken for granted understanding of stage of life: age categories are used to construct interpretations of individuals' experiences ([Gubrium, Holstein, & Buckholdt, 1994](#)). [Thell and Jacobsson \(2016\)](#) explored how, in the context of a psychological helpline, explicit inquiries about callers' age were used to ascribe them to specific SOL categories, which served as ground for interpretation about help-seekers' expectations and behaviours.

Overall, this above-mentioned literature suggests that 'doing age' in conversations can be used as a magnifying glass to unveil the insidious workings of culturally dominant age stereotypes in the workplace and to investigate the agentic role of social interaction in the maintenance and reproduction of ageism at work. As an analytical lens, 'doing age' shares some similarities with ethnographic methods, as shown by [Heinrichsmeier's \(2019\)](#) account of the subtle web of routines and expectations that constitute everyday interactions in older age. Both aim to expose the mundane, commonplace ageist assumptions towards older persons. Moreover, the fine-grained analysis of social interactions upon which 'doing age' is based disentangles ageism from the sheer insensitivity to age (e.g. 'rude comments') and reconnects discourse to the body: embodied age shapes interaction patterns based on dominant ageist views of both the young and the old.

Past research on 'doing age' has privileged medical or mundane settings, but we argue that there is significant potential for a more nuanced understanding of age and ageing in the workplace. Hence, we developed a study of social interactions in the context of PAIs at an Italian labour union. More specifically, we directed attention towards how managers and employees, in their situated encounters, utilised the category of age while taking turns in discussing performance at work.

Analytical settings: performance appraisal interviews

In line with our focus on 'doing age' at work and on the micro-dynamics of social interaction, we drew from the traditions of discourse and MCA ([Nikander, 2002](#)) and analysed the video recordings of PAIs at an Italian labour union. Fine-grained analysis of video recordings of naturally occurring data is, in fact, especially suited to investigating the construction of social categories in talk ([Stokoe, 2012](#)). In the analysis, we directed particular attention to how SOL categories were mobilised through the naturally occurring sequence of turns.

PAIs are yearly, usually dyadic, questionnaire-based meetings between a manager and an employee. From a conceptual perspective sensitive to the sequential analysis of conversations, PAIs constitute a particularly salient interactional arena where organisational norms and culture are actively enacted ([Sandlund, Olin-Scheller, Nyroos, Jakobsen, & Nahnfeldt, 2011](#)). Moreover, past research has shown that older workers experience ageism during performance review – especially regarding promotion and development evaluation ([Harris et al., 2018](#)) – and that managers disproportionately rely on age stereotypes to assess older workers' performance ([Loretto & White, 2006](#)). Therefore, the institutional agenda of assessing performance may increase the salience of age or the category-bounded attributes as a reasoning tool available in

conversation to both the appraiser and the appraisee. The conversational business of agreeing on the notions mobilised by categories is fundamental to establish common ground upon which performance evaluations can be justified and legitimated. The maintenance of this agreement is a key element of performance appraisal and, as demonstrated by [Ruusuvuori, Asmuß, Henttonen, and Ravaja \(2019\)](#), is of particular interest in this setting characterised by asymmetry between the manager and employee at both power and knowledge levels.

The organisation selected in the study was an Italian labour union, heretofore referred to as Workers United (WU). The choice of WU was especially poignant, as labour unions are organisations typically imbued with values and symbolic references that tend to be politically oriented ([Skarlicki & Latham, 1996](#)). Values of diversity, social inclusion, respect and anti-discrimination are usually founding ones: these should characterise a labour union as having an inclusive working environment where age is not a discriminatory factor. The PAIs were based on a template form commissioned to an external human resources (HR) consultancy firm, as shown in [Table 1](#). WU's employees were requested to individually self-evaluate according to this form, and their line managers performed their own independent evaluations on the same basis. The form included ten distinct evaluation categories and used a five-point scale. Previous studies on PAIs suggest that fixed performance evaluation categories produce the blocks on which the 'ideal employee' for a given organisation/workplace is constructed. [Sandlund et al. \(2011\)](#) highlighted that employees constantly need to portray themselves in a favourable light to adhere to organisational norms and expectations, as they seek confirmation by managers. Hence, the diverse mobilisation of age by employees and managers, and the likely tension between ideal identity and age identity for employees, makes performance appraisal an interesting institutional setting to investigate ageism.

Materials

The first author visited WU and negotiated access for the study, including permission to video record the performance appraisals. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Tampere Region. The first author was able get familiar with the work environment at WU and collected background information on the PAI practices (e.g. forms used in the evaluation and guidelines given to employees and managers) as

Table 1
Description of the participants of the performance appraisal interviews (PAIs). (*There are only two supervisors.)

Number of PAIs	Employee (pseudonym, role, gender, age)	Supervisor(s)* (pseudonym, role, gender, age)
1	Emilia, Director (woman centre), female, 48	Mario, HR manager, male, 45
2	Giorgio, Director (social policies), male, 40	HR manager
3	Corrado, Director (immigration office), male, 61	HR manager
4	Bruno, Director (insolvency proceeding office), male, 59	HR manager
5	Valentino, Director (organisational practices), male, 55	Gennaro, General officer, male, 49
6	Mario, HR manager, male, 45	General officer
7	Davide, Director (fiscal practices), male, 50	HR manager
8	Silvio, Responsible for local area, male, 59	HR manager, General officer
9	Luca, Responsible for local area, male, 53	HR manager, General officer
10	Lorenzo, Responsible for local area, male, 51	HR manager, General officer
11	Gianni, Director (dispute office), male, 46	HR manager
12	Veronica, Staff (HR assistant), female, 27	HR manager

well as interviewed the HR manager. These data sources allowed us to develop insights into WU's work practices, organisational culture and performance appraisal system, which informed our entire analytical and interpretive process. As a workplace, WU is profoundly rooted in its institutional function of being a labour union. Accordingly, its espoused values privilege the respect and protection of workers' rights, social inclusion and the maintenance and respect of a long-standing socialist tradition. Data collection took place at the service branch of WU – that is, the department within the union that offers services to private citizens, whether union members or not. As service providers, WU's employees are asked to engage with a productivity-based management system to enhance organisational efficiency and revenues. This expectation is linked to an ongoing process of restructuring and managerial re-orientation of WU's practices: in this context, the PAIs as studied below were introduced only two years prior to the data collection.

In line with our ethnomethodological approach, we recorded 12 PAIs that took place in June 2019 at WU. Overall, data collection generated 15.5 h of video recordings. Two managers were involved as appraisers: the HR manager and the political secretary, a leadership role typical in labour unions. Some interviews were conducted by one manager and some by both appraisers. In our data, we did not find any significant differences based on the presence of one or two evaluators, as when both were present, only one led the interview. Fig. 1 illustrates the recorded interactions. The employees were all 'white collar' and were responsible for a service. Table 2 describes the participants. Two video cameras were positioned in the interview room to acquire both the appraiser's and the appraisee's side of the interaction. Video cameras were employed with the aim of observing non-verbal interactions, such as gazes and body movement, but the focus of the analysis for this study was the verbal interaction among the interactants and their use of categories in conversation. For data collection, the first author set the video cameras in the interview room prior to the PAIs but was not physically present during the interviews. All study participants were informed about the study, its aims and the methods of data collection prior to the PAIs and signed an informed consent form regarding future data use. Participants were informed that the focus of the study was the use of age and other personal categories in formal interactions at work. They were assured of confidentiality and that they could withdraw at any time and interrupt the recording without consequence. The researcher also clearly stated that the participants and their talk, gestures and behaviours were not under trial or subject to judgement and evaluation other than for the stated purposes of the study.

Analytical method

In line with our chosen approach and our focus on interactional micro-dynamics, we adopted MCA as our key analytical method (Sack, 1972). First developed as a participant-oriented investigation of social relations in everyday interactions, MCA is increasingly used in the social sciences to investigate the constitutive relationship between social action and language (Cromdal et al., 2018). Sequentially examining

Table 2

Categories of performance evaluation obtained from the form provided to employees and managers.

N	Category	Description
1	Professional leadership	Ability to be reliable and recognised as a professional reference point by colleagues and managers.
2	People management	Ability to adapt the management style to fit the people and the situations that need to be managed.
3	Decision-making	Ability to take prompt and fitting decisions within your competency and your mandates while respecting the normative and organisational limits and the relations with your supervisor.
4	Results orientation	Ability to address your working activities towards the achievement of your goals
5	Planning and programming	Ability to identify and organise your activities, define priorities and develop actions.
6	Flexibility and innovation	Ability to respond to organisational complexity through a flexible approach and to be open to modifying your behaviours and innovating working strategies.
7	Communication and management of information	Ability to conveniently filter information, thus effectively transferring content without ambiguity, and to modulate your communication style on the basis of the context and of the speakers.
8	Development orientation	Ability to recognise the gaps that affect your own role and the openness to develop actions towards the development of your own knowledge and professional skills.
9	Systemic view and integration	Ability to create integration inside the organisation based on the situation, your behaviours and your role in the wider organisational context.
10	Sense of belonging and engagement	Ability to transfer images and content to share the knowledge of the activities developed inside the organisation and to spread the political and civic orientation of the organisation.

interactions allows investigations into the performative aspects of discourse: in MCA, discourse becomes talk-in-interaction. Membership categories are descriptors organised in systematic collections called 'devices'. For instance, 'stages of life' is considered a membership categorisation device that entails an ordered collection of subcategories, such as 'senior', 'adult' and 'teenager', which are perceived as ordered along institutionalised life course trajectories.

According to Sack (1972), categories have features that are crucial to their functioning in that each category is culturally linked to a set group of practices and activities (i.e. category-bound activities) or attributes (i.e. category-bound attributes). For instance, the category 'adult' is culturally linked to activities such as working and taking care of children, whereas the category 'teenager' relates to enjoying free time and breaking rules. Therefore, category-bound activities and category-bound attributes constitute powerful discursive resources in interactions: the mere act of uttering a category-bounded activity or predicate is sufficient for the participants to establish an association with the paired categorisation device because members of the same culture share the same domain of cultural knowledge and vocabulary.

In accordance with MCA, we directed our analytical efforts towards exploring how WU's managers and employees 'did age' (Nikander, 2009; Sandlund et al., 2011) by mobilising SOL categorisation devices in interactions in their PAIs. WU's employees and managers share both the wider cultural norms of Italian society and the specific organisational culture of their workplace: they are, therefore, likely to share a deep-rooted cultural understanding of the notions mobilised by SOL categorisation devices in-situ. Moreover, by agreeing or resisting to be ascribed to such categories, employees accomplish social actions linked to

Fig. 1. Disposition of the interactants in the performance appraisals interviews.

performance negotiation – for example, they account for negative or positive performances on different tasks. This means that in addition to constructing situated meanings of age-related categories in their conversations, WU's employees agree or disagree on a specific 'doing' of age and engage in social action (e.g. explaining, justifying and corroborating) accordingly.

Data analysis involved several stages. The first author initially watched the video recordings and transcribed them according to standard MCA using Jefferson's (2004) transcription symbols. The same author then engaged in repeated viewings and readings of the entire dataset with the objective of identifying all the extracts where the speakers – that is, WU's managers and employees – mobilised categories related to age and SOL. Finally, the authors collaboratively reviewed the extracts and identified the three modalities presented in the results below.

Results: 'doing age' in performance appraisal interactions at WU

Our analysis identified three main ways in which SOL categories were used during PAIs at WU: quantification of the number of years on the job/within the organisation, 'ageing within the organisation' and age-group membership identification.

Quantification

Quantification entailed the mobilisation of numerical labels and, more specifically, the overt quantification of age or seniority in the PAIs. This pattern is shown in Extract 1a below that reports the conversation between a male employee – Giorgio (GIO), a manager – and his direct superior – Mario (MAR), the HR manager. This part of the conversation referred to the section in the performance evaluation form dedicated to professional authorship and decision-making. The extract starts with Giorgio explaining his self-evaluation to Mario:

1 GIO: †but I think I am: >also compared to the team that
2 I manage< (.) it is acknowledged to me
3 >I feel that< it is acknowledged to me the author-
4 the professional authority
5 †also considering the experience (.) that I have
6 mm: (.) that I have developed (.)
7 as director (.01) of Division One
8 (.03)
9 ee: (.) also about the decision making
10 I think (.01) I reach (.) a high level
11 mainly because I evaluate >I have learned<
12 after twenty years [that I am in this organisation
13 [(MAR starts nodding)]
14 I have learned to evaluate
15 every single aspect

Giorgio initiates this interaction round by reporting his self-evaluation. Lines 1–3 exemplify a recurring pattern in WU's PAIs: if positive, self-evaluations are always reported as a feeling or a thought and are never delivered as objective statements. Here, Giorgio changes his initial phrase 'it is acknowledged' to 'I feel that it is acknowledged', and this change from impersonal/objective to personal/subjective marks the surfacing of moral considerations into the ongoing performance evaluation. Giorgio characterises his positive self-evaluation in terms of 'professional authority' (line 4) and corroborates his statement by appealing to age as experience (i.e. 'also considering the experience

that I have'). Here, experience – a category-implicative descriptor (Stokoe, 2012) for age – is used to justify a positive evaluation on professional authority.

Giorgio deploys the same line of argumentation in relation to decision-making (line 9). Here, Giorgio utilises the explanatory remark 'after twenty years that I am in this organisation...I have learned' (lines 12–14). Giorgio's disclosure of the exact number of years of experience at WU follows several indirect references to a lengthy process of experience accumulation. Giorgio relies on quantification as a discursive resource to legitimate (Nikander, 2002) his subjective positive self-evaluation as manager. Quantification, in fact, directs the interactants' attention to a taken-for-granted cultural link between accumulations, numbers and value. In turn, Mario accepts this through silent nodding, showing support for his interpretation. Note that Giorgio frames his self-evaluation 'also in comparison to the theme that I manage' (lines 1–2), thereby suggesting an interpretive context for Mario's sense-making. Giorgio's subsequent references to his accumulation of experience and quantification are more meaningful and carry greater value when compared to younger, less experienced colleagues.

Quantification also appears below in Extract 1b that shows another male employee – Davide (DAV), a manager and team leader – discussing his performance with Mario, WU's HR manager. This excerpt features near the end of the self-evaluation report, in relation to the item 'sense of belonging' in the evaluation form.

1 DAV: about the rest (.02)
2 the systemic vision is what I have::
3 limited to my (.) capacity
4 >the sense of belonging
5 instead I feel it greatl[y]<
6 MAR: ° [well] of cours[e] °
7 DAV: [eh] you
8 know: I have spent a life
9 you know a part of my life inside here
10 and you know
11 MAR: ° <how many years in total in Workers United?> °
12 DAV: since '88 so we are talking about 31 years well::
13 MAR: dang 31 years.
14 DAV: like almost like a home
15 but a:n important part of you
16 and >from this point of view<
17 I have never had: (.)
18 second thoughts doubts, (.) demotivation,

Davide frames this section by stating he 'feels greatly' the 'sense of belonging' (line 4), and Mario vocally affiliates with this self-evaluation by means of the expression 'of course' (line 6). Davide, in turn, feeling the support of the manager, further elaborates and provides additional explanations using 'life' (line 8) as a category-implicative descriptor for the years spent at WU. By means of this descriptor, Davide can convey both the 'length' of his work experience and the importance that it has for him. This statement is, however, immediately tempered when Davide switches from 'life' to 'part of my life' (line 9), suggesting the need to soften the description. Mario's response to Davide's rephrasing is to ask a direct question that elicits the explicit quantification of the number of years Davide has spent at WU (line 11). In the following exchange, Davide's quantification (i.e. '31 years'; line 12) and Mario's reiteration of it (line 13) reveal how both share the same cultural norm

that attributes positive value to higher number of years in terms of experience, which is associated with a higher sense of belonging.

Extract 1b also shows how Davide used an interactional resource – the expression ‘you know’ in lines 7–10 – to suggest implicit agreement. The expression ‘you know’ is recognised as a marker of a speaker’s epistemic stance (Landgrebe, 2012) – that is, the rhetorical use of knowledge or how knowledge is oriented as an accountable matter (Melander Bowden & Sandlund, 2019). As highlighted by research on institutional meetings (Asmuß, 2011), speakers use ‘you know’ to suggest shared knowledge when they are intent on pursuing agreement. Here, Davide assumes a knowing stance when talking about his ‘life’ at WU and before engaging in exact quantification: this discursive move prompts Mario to inquire further and, in turn, gives Davide the opportunity to articulate and legitimise his positive self-evaluation by quantification.

Overall, our analysis shows that quantification is used as age categorisation only when discussing specific items of the PAI form – namely, professional leadership, decision-making and sense of belonging. This suggests that at WU, employees mobilise age in the discussion of performance items in a fashion that aligns with commonly held positive stereotypes of older workers, who are often viewed as experienced, highly committed and reliable (Truxillo, Finkelstein, Pytlovany, & Jenkins, 2016).

Ageing within the organisation

Appraisees also utilised the categorisation ‘ageing within the organisation’ to support their self-evaluation on the item ‘openness to novelty’ in the performance evaluation form. In particular, WU’s employees used this categorisation that conveys the idea of the passage of a significant length of time – a category-implicative descriptor (Stokoe, 2009) – to justify their lack of openness to innovation. Extract 2a below shows Bruno (BRU) – a male employee – addressing ‘flexibility and innovation’ with Mario, the HR manager:

1 BRU: and so well. >on flexibility and innovation<
 2 =also here: e: how to say (.03)
 3 mmm I could improve >a bit probably<
 4 with the passing of the years maybe
 5 maybe also hhh an(h) a a disposition
 6 let’s say so t- to be less
 7 how to say less (.) .hhh
 8 ready here to to welcome the things .hh
 9 and so also this let’s say
 10 this could be improvable.
 11 >this said however< e:
 12 I don:t d- don’t have a
 13 °|pre-established idea° †no
 14 so e .h I am (.) I think to be °|welcoming°
 15 in the moment that
 16 I receive an input [that]
 17 MAR: [of c]ourse of course
 18 BRU: that comes >maybe from others<
 19 e: that could be in some way helpful
 20 for everybody here.

By openly admitting that he ‘could improve’ (line 3) on ‘flexibility and innovation’ (line 1), Bruno directs Mario’s attention to a professional weakness and then uses the categorisation ‘with the passing of years’ (line 4) as justification for his negative performance. The reiteration of expressions such as ‘how to say’, ‘let’s say’, ‘here’ and ‘maybe’ (lines 5–7) emphasises the delicacy of the exposing negative performance evaluation. In this epistemic arena, Bruno’s use of the age categorisation ‘passing of years’ to justify negative performance aligns with wider societal, taken-for-granted norms and stereotypes about older peoples’ lower interest and ability to be innovative and flexible (Truxillo et al., 2016). Bruno tries to dissociate himself from these negative stereotypes by suggesting that he ‘however’ does not have ‘pre-established ideas’ and ‘is welcoming’. Bruno distinguishes between two dimensions of ‘flexibility and innovation’: ‘welcome the things’ (line 7) – an action descriptor – and ‘not have pre-established idea’ (line 10) – a trait descriptor. Through this verbal construction, he suggests that the ‘passing of time’ at WU has affected his routines and behavioural patterns at work and, therefore, engendered lower openness to novelty, whereas his personal traits – including open-mindedness – are unaltered.

Mario, in turn, verbally agrees with Bruno’s accounts (‘of course of course’; line 17), and his lack of reaction when faced with a negative self-evaluation based on ageist stereotyping suggests that he shares the same norms. In line with extant research suggesting that younger managers favour employees of the same age (Principi & Fabbietti, 2015), it could be argued that the age difference between Mario and Bruno may be at issue here: as a younger manager evaluating an older employee, Mario is using negative stereotypes about older workers (Truxillo et al., 2016) in his work practice.

Extract 2b below shows a male employee, Corrado (COR), discussing the item ‘welcoming others’ ideas’ listed in the performance evaluation form with two appraisers, Mario (MAR), the HR manager, and Gennaro (GEN), the general political officer:

1 COR: >so< about the management of complex issues
 2 I think I can do it. (.01)
 3 I am open to welcome others' idea (01.)
 4 I have put generally exactly because (.) and
 5 >how to say< being (.) thinking to be
 6 the person most informed on the topic (.)
 7 how to say I am open but not <not always>(.)
 8 <not always>.

In earlier parts of the PAI, Corrado repeatedly emphasised his experience and wisdom, linking both qualities to the passing of years – an age categorisation (see Extract 2a) – at work within WU as well as outside of the workplace. Here, Corrado continues in the same vein and links being the person ‘most informed on the topic’ – a category-implicative descriptor for age and ageing within an organisation – with his performance in terms of openness to other people's ideas. As observed in Bruno's case above, Corrado also utilises various verbal expressions (‘how to say’; lines 5 and 7) and repairs (‘being’ – ‘thinking to be’; line 5) to articulate a negative self-evaluation on openness. The sequencing of his argument moves from an initial reference to the performance item under discussion to an explanatory account of behaviour at work (lines 4–6), which results in a fundamentally negative overall evaluation. This is followed by an attempt at toning down the negativity (line 7): Corrado describes himself as ‘open’, albeit ‘not always-not always’. The reiteration of ‘not always’, however, has the opposite effect.

Unlike Bruno – who associated lack of openness to a routinisation of behaviour at work owing to the time spent at WU – Corrado links his own lack of openness to other people's inexperience: because of the comparatively short time they have spent at WU, Corrado's colleagues are less experienced, lack good-quality ideas and ultimately affect his performance as well as their own. During this short interaction, Corrado ‘does’ age by using the length of time spent at WU as a proxy for experience and by deploying this categorisation to construct a complex justification for his poor performance. This involves the combination of two ageist stereotypes: on the one hand, Corrado mobilises the positive stereotype that links experience with older workers' wisdom (against younger workers' ‘bad ideas’); on the other, he reinforces the negative stereotype about older workers' scarce innovativeness and flexibility.

Overall, our analysis shows that age, as the passing of years working at WU, is typically linked to the accumulation of experience in a linear progression with positive qualitative and quantitative connotations. Accumulated experience may, however, result in both negative and positive outcomes, depending on its characterisation: as a proxy for routinisation, it is used by older workers as a barrier to being innovative; as a proxy for wisdom, human capital or knowledge (Backes-Gellner et al., 2011), it is mobilised to attribute positive value to older workers' participation in the workplace.

Age-group membership identification

The third categorisation identified in our analysis entails the explicit identification with a specific age-group – namely, ‘younger’ or ‘older’ workers; by assigning to themselves or others a membership category based on age, the interactants ascribe age and all the stereotypical features of the referenced group as interpretative resources for performance evaluation. Interestingly, membership ascription is done differently by managers and employees: in the case of WU's PAIs, our analysis shows that age-group categories were used by managers to praise good employees' performance and by employees for both positive and negative self-evaluation. In Extract 3a below, Mario (MAR) – the HR manager – is evaluating a female employee, Emilia (EMI), about her ‘sense of

belonging’ to WU, a specific item in the union's performance evaluation form:

1 MAR: †you have (.) as I see you
 2 a strong sense of organisation
 3 you were saying it also before
 4 when you go around saying I am Workers United
 5 this awareness is rooted in you.
 6 a thing that maybe lacks
 7 e:: more for example if I think
 8 >about the younger colleagues
 9 that have started in our organisation recently<
 10 .h this thi:ng <lacks even> †right
 11 also in the older ones

Using the comparative ‘to the younger colleagues’ (line 8), Mario assigns himself and Emilia to the ‘the older workers’ age group, an inference-rich category that mobilises stereotypical characteristics commonly associated with the group (Nikander, 2002). More specifically, this attribution mobilises different SOL as positioning categories that allow members to express positive or negative evaluations based on shared social norms and expectations about life course trajectories (Sacks, 1974). Mario refers to age groups to support his positive evaluation of Emilia's performance on the item ‘sense of belonging’ (line 2), and this categorisation aligns with employers' stereotypical views of older workers as more loyal and committed (e.g. Bal, Reiss, Rudolph, & Baltes, 2011). Mario's use of the verb ‘rooted’ is indicative of a taken-for-granted link between age and ‘sense of organisation’. Through a generalisation discursive device (‘more for example if I think’; line 7), Mario positions himself and Emilia in the same age group and, ultimately, in the same positive evaluation as loyal WU employees. Perhaps aware of the danger of explicit age stereotyping at work – given that workplaces are supposedly regarded as age-neutral environments – Mario ends his speech by making an explicit reference to ‘older’ colleagues who might also lack a deep sense of the organisation (line 11).

In Extract 3b below, the general officer, Gennaro, refers to older workers as an out-group to emphasise the atypical positive performance of WU's HR manager, Mario, here in the role of appraisee. Gennaro and Mario discuss one of the items of the evaluation form, the ability to take responsibility for one's own action as part of ‘professional leadership’:

1 GEN: you take complete responsibility
 2 for your actions. (.)
 3 >taking responsibility also
 4 for what i:s not< yours.
 5 one of the biggest defects
 6 of the labour union workers (.)
 7 >'it would be nice to explain
 8 why this happens'
 9 especially to the ones of a certain age<=
 10 is that sometimes
 11 they are very tie to their competencies
 12 but they find it difficult (.)
 13 to recognise their mistakes.

Here, Gennaro uses the same discursive strategy as shown in Extract 3a, but the object of appraisal and evaluation is older workers, who are generally perceived as unable to take charge of their actions. The deployment of a double set of stereotypes – whereby ageism is compounded by the belief that labour unions' organisational culture is typically anti-meritocratic – allows Gennaro to boost his positive evaluation: Mario is distinctly unique as an effective leader in two respects: as both a younger worker and a member of a labour union organisation.

In Extract 3c below, Corrado – the same employee that appears in Extract 2b – uses age-group membership categories to support his positive self-evaluation on 'communication', another item of WU's evaluation form for PAIs.

1 COR: most of the staff in the area
 2 is is retired
 3 so <with the BIG heart that
 4 you can recognise to them>
 5 but sometimes
 6 I have difficulties let's say to organise them.
 7 (...)
 8 <it's not enough> <it's not enough>
 9 the massive communication
 10 let's say that with some type o:f of workers
 11 >generally< with people with another age
 12 and with another <↑technological> education
 13 absolutely would be enough

Corrado, who is 59 years old, uses the age-group category and life-stage device 'retired' (line 2) to set a comparison with an out-group he does not belong to (Nikander, 2002). Despite having previously attributed to himself some of the positive qualities stereotypically associated with older workers – for instance, accumulated knowledge and competence – in this interactional segment, Corrado distances himself from the old-age group 'retirees'. The membership category 'retiree' is described as 'having a big heart' (line 3) but also as difficult to organise and as lacking competence (lines 6 and 10, respectively). This attribution aligns

with dominant organisational and societal norms that stereotype and discriminate against older workers (e.g. Cuddy, Norton, & Fiske, 2005). Corrado is using language to separate himself and his positive performance from 'older colleagues' that he shares the same chronological age category with but that he now stereotypes to set himself apart. His excerpt entails more than simply assigning age stereotypes to a category (Nikander, 2009; Stokoe & Edwards, 2009) and encompasses legitimising such claims by mobilising discursive resources as an extreme case formulation ('absolutely' in line 11; see Pomerantz, 1986). Interestingly, the use of an age-group category such as 'of another age' (line 9) mobilised the notion that the old worker stereotype stands for and indeed summarises a whole host of undesirable behaviours and attitudes at work. The manager does not take an open stance towards the use of age stereotypes in this interactional arena, which suggests at the bare minimum a shared cultural understanding of ageing and age at work.

Overall, our analysis shows that age-group membership is used in PAIs at WU to infer (Jayyusi, 1985) and mobilise cultural notions about age that are fundamentally associated with positive and negative stereotypes about older/younger workers (Stokoe & Edwards, 2009). The interactional analysis shows how such norms operated at the broad level of society but were also influenced by, and embedded in, the situated organisational culture of WU as a labour union.

Discussion

Our study investigated how age is 'done' at the micro level of conversations during PAIs and explored the use of SOL as an interpretative device. Overall, our analysis shows that in the case of WU, age was mobilised as an argumentative resource during PAIs in three different ways: quantitatively as a number, as passing of time and as an oppositional 'young'/'old' membership category ascription. More specifically, three findings emerge as especially notable. First, different forms of age categorisation are associated with different items/sections of the performance evaluation form used at WU. Second, age categorisation is used differently to argue for positive or negative evaluation depending on the performance item being discussed and the role as appraisee or appraiser taken by the participant 'doing' it. Third, age categorisation is rooted in the specific setting of WU and its organisational culture.

First, our findings show that age categorisation is done differently depending on the performance item under discussion as articulated in the evaluation form adopted for the PAIs: quantification of employment is mobilised by WU's employees to account for leadership and sense of belonging, 'ageing within the organisation' (e.g. the passing of time) is mobilised by WU's employees in connection with openness to innovation, and older and younger workers' membership identification is mobilised by managers to appraise the sense of belonging and leadership and by employees to discuss communication and technology use. In other words, WU's performance evaluation form pre-structures the interaction that occurs during the face-to-face interviews and can be regarded as agentic in the complex process of the social construction of age at work. Our study therefore adds to previous research showing that institutions and institutional actors are constructed by documents (Alasuutari, 2015) and that their texts are activated by their readers. According to Smith (2005), texts enter and coordinate people's doing: WU's performance evaluation form is age-neutral in that it does not overtly incorporate age as an evaluation category, but it shapes interactions in a way that engenders the stereotypical 'doing' of age through talk by the participants. The evaluation form is, in other words, modelled on the ageless notion of an ideal worker (Nyroos & Sandlund, 2014; Ruusuvaari et al., 2019) but actively contributes to the maintenance and reproduction of ageist stereotypes: this sheds light on the difference between age-equal and age-blind work practices, whereby micro-dynamics based on stereotypical notions of age can be accepted despite the nominal equality of the workplace. This finding also contributes to the study of PAIs as an institutional practice. The link identified between given age categorisations and specific performance

dimensions – as expressed by the items of the evaluation form – suggests the need for the critical analysis of the guidelines used in HR practices that incorporates the micro-dynamics of power. In the interactional arena of a performance appraisal, templates might reproduce the existing asymmetries of power rather than promoting inclusivity.

Second, our analysis shows how WU's employees and managers 'did' age and acted socially to support and legitimise positive and/or negative performance evaluations. Further, different types of age categorisation transferred the positive or negative character of their underlying age-based stereotype to the positive or negative character of the performance evaluation (Ng & Feldman, 2012). This suggests that age categorisation constitutes an argumentative resource that can be mobilised at work to negotiate an acceptable role identity as an ideal worker and/or fair (that is, 'neutral' and objective) manager. This finding complements previous studies on the difference between chronological age and perceived age at work (Krekula, 2019; Kunze, Boehm, & Bruch, 2021) suggesting that chronological age is not an objective criterion in employees' evaluation and categorisation, whereas personal age, based on age identity at work, has more influence on job and organisational outcomes. It also aligns with discursive studies on age that highlight the role of the micro-dynamics of power in the construction of age-based identity (e.g. Krekula, 2009; Spedale, 2019). On the one hand, this finding contributes to problematising the victim–perpetrator paradigm that dominates mainstream literature on ageism at work and casts managers as perpetrators and older workers as victims of discrimination (Riach & Kelly, 2015). On the other hand, it sheds light on the complexity of these dynamics by showing how interaction actively shapes the dynamics beyond its usually recognised function as a context for dynamics of identity and power. Furthermore, these considerations are potentially extended beyond verbal interactions to encompass non-verbal communications, highlighting the role that the body play (Streeck, Goodwin, & LeBaron, 2011) in interactions and, ultimately, in the 'doing' of age at work.

Finally, our analysis shows how 'doing age' during PAIs at WU was rooted in broader cultural references and norms – such as dominant societal stereotypes about older and younger workers – as well as in those specific to WU's situated organisational and institutional culture. This corroborates previous studies that show how practice is influenced not only by organisational actors' chronological age (Principi & Fabbiotti, 2015) but also by the 'age' and history of the organisation they inhabit (Lawrence, 1996). For instance, Lawrence (1996) maintained that age profiles are linked to age norms in institutional settings, which, consequently, construct expectations, sanctions and grouping. This expectation is deeply tied to the notion of ideal employees and, consequently, to the managerial agenda driving PAIs. Hence, organisational practices and acquired routines can reproduce age as a significant organising principle, which makes age norms shared knowledge and, therefore, allows for the use of ageist reference in interaction to find common ground and foster interactional alignment.

Conclusion

Our study explores how age is 'done' in organisations when individuals mobilise stage-of-life and age-related categories during conversational micro-interactions such as PAIs. Besides contributing to the literature on age and ageism as a discursive and relational phenomenon (e.g. Spedale et al., 2014) and on organisations as done in interactions (e.g. Schoeneborn, Kuhn, & Kärreman, 2019), our study expands the field of discursive gerontology and the methodological toolkit (Heinrichsmeier, 2018; Krekula, 2009; Näslund, 2017; Nikander, 2009; Thell & Jacobsson, 2016) available to scholars interested in investigating age and ageism at work. Furthermore, our research has several pragmatic implications, mostly related to how interaction processes reflect and reinforce organisational norms.

First, understanding how societal age norms interact with situated organisational norms is useful for bringing age management into

everyday use. HR professionals are responsible for constructing work environments that are inclusive and diverse. By showing how ageism at work is reproduced in and through interactions between employers and employees and by linking these dynamics to elements of evaluation, we direct attention towards ageism as a tripartite phenomenon of prejudice, stereotypes and discrimination (Officer, Thiagarajan, Schneiders, Nash, & de la Fuente-Núñez, 2020). Our analysis will be fed back to the participants and to WU in general to promote a more nuanced understanding of how interaction shapes, or indeed constructs, age at work. Similar lines of inquiry could be followed to promote and enable greater diversity and inclusion in other workplaces.

Second, our study has implications for performance appraisal as a specific managerial practice. For example, the use of apparently neutral forms that surreptitiously foster the reproduction and maintenance of discriminatory stereotypes – whether based on age or other categories of marginalisation – should be subject to critical scrutiny. A more nuanced appreciation of the interactional dynamics of 'doing age' at work may overcome some of the limitations of the current age-blind practices and enhance equal career progression. Educational/developmental needs are usually discussed in performance appraisal interactions and biased processes may endanger their outcomes and, for example, reduce the access to training that has been identified as a strategic element for older workers' retention (Lazazzara & Bombelli, 2011). This calls for an approach to performance evaluation that recognises heterogeneity in the social construction of age and ageing (Previtali et al., 2020) and moves beyond the simplistic dynamic of victimisation.

Our analysis, grounded in a social constructionist approach to working life, does not limit the study but poses organic constraints. Generating data and performing analysis with a specific focus on ageism might lead to an overestimation of this phenomenon. Our collaborative approach to analysis and interpretation has, however, promoted reflexivity and contributed to the credibility and overall validity to our findings through continuous discussions and reciprocal cross-validation. Note also that the study does not intend to locate and isolate 'guilty' parties. On the contrary, it aims to highlight the co-construction of the stereotypical use of age in job performance appraisal and evaluation. The chosen ethnomethodological approach, while allowing for direct focus on interactional dynamics, poses constraints in terms of the size of the available dataset, which is limited owing to the complexity of the recording logistics and the requirements of detailed conversation analysis. Similar studies could be conducted in the same type of organisational setting with a larger group of participants to validate our outcomes and the identified interaction patterns. In addition, our analysis focuses on age as a potential category of discrimination at work while excluding others, particularly gender. Although the gender composition did not allow for gender-related dynamics to clearly emerge from our analysis, we acknowledge that gendered ageism is inherently linked with ageing in the workplace. Future research should strive to include more women as well as different organisational settings and national contexts to expand our understanding of how age norms operate in the workplace and in performance evaluation. Finally, we recognise the difficulties and demands entailed by our proposed approach, including access and ethical approval. Adhering to ethical guidelines requires informing participants of the subject of the study: when investigating stereotypes and prejudices at work, this might expose them to risk and enhance their vulnerability. Although the presence of video cameras can alter the natural flow of conversation, this was not observed during the PAIs analysed in this study. Further, the strength of interactional analysis lies precisely in its being in situ and, consequently, shedding light on age and ageism at work as a fundamentally contextual and situational phenomenon.

Overall, we believe that our analysis showcases the power of MCA as an overlooked approach for the study of ageing and working life. We call for future research to be conducted from a critical perspective towards organisations, age and ageism and to move beyond experimental designs and researcher-generated data to naturally occurring data when

studying employer–employee relationships. Future research might benefit from the observational ethnographic methods in the exploration of actual work practices to shed light on the discursive construction of age in mundane everyday interactions as well as to raise consciousness of the implicit and explicit ways in which ageism is socially constructed in the workplace.

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Appendix A. Transcription symbols (Jefferson, 2004)

Symbol	Description
(.)	A micropause
(0.2)	A timed pause (seconds)
∩	Speech overlaps
(O)	Comments or annotations of non-verbal actions
> <	The pace of speech has quickened
< >	The pace of speech has slowed down
<u>word</u>	A raise in volume or emphasis
↑	Rise in intonation
↓	Drop in intonation
(h)	Laughter in the conversation
∴	Stretched sound
°word°	Quieter than surrounding speech by the same speaker
hhh	In-breath
.hhh	Out-breath
whord	Aspiration/breathiness if within a word
w(h)ord	Laughing while talking

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